

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Triyandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol. XIV, Book. III -IV

JULY - DECEMBER 2022

SRET

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

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Manuscriptology: An Overview

Dr. Keerthi P,¹ Prof. Ramadas P.V².

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Abstract

The scientific or structural study of handwritten documents having a modest amount of antiquity is known as Manuscriptology. In our country, only 5% of the texts that are available have been made available to the public. According to a study by the National Manuscript Mission, there are more than 20000 Ayurvedic manuscripts that have been found but have not yet been studied. The field of Manuscriptology offers a wide range of opportunities for ayurveda. Only 2% of medical manuscripts are printed, thus steps should be taken to preserve, categorise, critically edit, and publish Ayurvedic manuscripts. Doing so will pave the way for future research efforts in the field of Ayurveda, including successful clinical studies.

Keywords

Manuscriptology, Ayurveda Manuscripts.

Introduction

Communication is essential for human existences; it can be conducted by oral and written tradition. Ayurveda being an ancient science has got both oral and written tradition for dissemination of

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knowledge. Manuscriptology is the scientific and structural study of hand written documents credited with fair antiquity. Treasures of wisdom have passed from generation to next generation by oral tradition and then written on different plant leaves and other materials. Paper usage became popular by the end of the 13th century AD. Till then various other materials are used for transferring knowledge. Manuscripts are one of the types of written tradition and are valuable treasures of knowledge. They are sources of cultural heritage and history. Their proper preservation is mandatory. 'Manus' means hands and 'Script' means written. So, any handwritten document is called a manuscript. That means any book or document or piece of any intellectual work written by hand rather than typed or printed or author's handwritten or typed that has not yet been published. Manuscriptology is the scientific or structural study of hand written documents credited with fair antiquity.

Manuscript Wealth of India

The following estimations were developed based on one of the surveys conducted by Dr. S.C. Biswas and Mr. M.K. Prajapathi on behalf of INTACH between 1988 and 1990. There are 50,000 manuscripts in India. 67% are Sanskrit manuscripts, 25% are various Indian languages, and the remaining 8% are Arabic-Tibetan languages. And the fact is that, many of these manuscripts are catalogued but still many are yet to be published or catalogued.

History of Manuscripts

From ancient times, knowledge systems in India have been transmitted down through a rich oral tradition to future generations. With the decline of oral transmission and the development of script and writing materials, this knowledge was transformed to written form on stone, papyrus, parchment, birch bark, palm leaves, and paper. Indians have been practicing writing for about four thousand years. The treasure of wisdom has been passed down to humanity in the form of manuscripts. They are written in many Indian languages and can be found all over the country in various organisations, libraries, monasteries, temples, and private collections. Manuscripts were widely copied with no restrictions on the script that was used to prevent them from being lost over time. Manuscripts were also copied in local scripts and those evolved in time and different

geographical areas.

Need For Manuscript Study

1. Since most of Indian knowledge is in the form of manuscripts, there is a strong need to preserve ancient knowledge and review the past.
2. Through Manuscriptology, addition of ancient knowledge to the current science is possible i.e., to contribute to the literary resources of various branches of science.
3. Manuscriptology will help in better understanding of principles related to Ayurveda.

Nature of Manuscripts

1. Palm leaf (tala patra)
2. Birch tree bark (burja patra)
3. Cotton cloth (karpasa patra)
4. Wooden planks (kasta palaka)
5. Copper plate (tamra patra)
6. Stone plate (sila patra)
7. Brick plate (mrittika)
8. Paper (kagaz)
9. Agar tree bark (sanchi patra)
10. Rock edits (sila lekha)
11. Skin (charma)

Preservation of Manuscripts

I. Physical methods

1. Preservation in glass racks and wooden boards.
2. Exposure to sufficient sunlight and air circulation.
3. By using butter paper in between pages which are very old to prevent sticking of papers.

II. Chemical methods

1. Chemical treatment by fumigation chambers.
2. By thymol acid chloromate solution.
3. Pest control by DDT spray, 5% mercuric chloride solu-

tion.

III. Microfilming

IV. Digitalization

1. By xeroxing.
2. By scanning.

Factors That Cause Deterioration of Manuscripts

1. Climatic condition – low humidity with heat destroys manuscripts.
2. Dust and atmospheric pollution.
3. Human carelessness.
4. Poor storage condition.
5. Pests like fungus, termites, ants, rats etc.

Order of Development of Manuscripts

1. Oral transmission.
2. Writing on clay and rocks.
3. Palm leaves and tree barks.
4. Started to use paper.
5. Latest modern edition by computer.

Importance of Manuscript

1. Manuscripts are evidence of our great ancient sciences. India has around 5 million manuscripts, making it the world's largest storehouse of manuscripts.
2. An estimated 10,000 manuscripts have been produced from 1500 A.D. to 1900 A.D., out of which 1/10th is traced.
3. Among lakhs of manuscripts related to Ayurveda, only 2% manuscripts are published.

Physical Attributes of A Manuscript

Manuscript has got two components.

1. Adheya (Scripts) - The older scripts are found in 'Brahmi lipi' and 'Kharoshti lipi'. 'Brahmi lipi' later developed into two streams, Devanagiri in the north and Grantha in south.
2. Adhara (Writing apparatus) – There are three components

related to writing apparatus.

3. Lekhya samagri (Writing surface) – Includes rock edits, writings done on stone plates, brick plates, copper plates, bark of trees, palm leaves, paper, cloth etc.
4. Lekhana samagri (Instruments used for writing) – Includes stylus, pen, brush etc.
5. Rakshana samagri (Materials used for binding) – The material used for binding the manuscripts.

Steps For Collection of Data, Digital Edition, Translation and Critical Edition of Manuscript.

1. Check the extent of availability of selected manuscripts in catalogues.
2. Carry out portal and electronic correspondence to libraries.
3. By follow up, the data i.e., photocopy of manuscript or in digital form along with consent can be obtained.
4. Digital edition of manuscript can be done using photo manipulation software like Adobe Photo- shop in which colour, background etc. needs to be done.
5. The collected manuscripts may be in different languages. Editing of manuscripts is impossible when it is in different languages. So translation should be done to a more understandable language so that more people can understand it.
6. Critical edition is done in two main ways namely lower criticism and higher criticism.

Following critical editing, the edited manuscript is published. Publishing is a form of documentation that can be used to progress research.

Lower Criticism

Lower criticism is done by four steps Heuristics, Collation, Emendation and Recension.

Heuristics

It means to find or to discover. It is the collection and analysis of all available evidence with respect to the text being edited.

Collation

Character by character comparison of two or more texts and to establish the relationship they bear to one another. Thus, collation is the process of comparison which gives rise to a set of variant readings for the text under consideration.

Emendation

A researcher suggests a reading as more possible to be close to the original on the basis of internal and external possibilities. **Recension:** It is the process of choosing among the variants i.e., process of choosing the best which is original or closer to the author's intention. It can also be described as critical revision of the text, review of the text or edited version.

Higher Criticism

It involves the assessment of the author's original work and it involves the following aspects.

1. The way in which the author delivers his or her work.
2. The environment in which the work was created.
3. The circumstances that prompted the author to compose it.
4. The author's life and the influence of other authors
5. The language employed.
6. The work contains literary elements.
7. The Work sources
8. The author's equipment.

Understanding Ayurvedic Manuscripts

Ayurveda being an age-old science is believed to be recollected by Lord Brahma, who in turn passed it over to Daksha Prajapati, Aswini Kumaras, Lord Indra, Atreya and finally Agnivesa etc. Thus, the main means of passing the divine science was mainly from the mouth of Gurus to the ear of the Shishya i.e., Oral transmission. Later, the extraordinarily brilliant Shishyas made an effort in preserving this knowledge and compiled their own works in the form of writing and inscriptions on different surfaces. Knowledge of Ayurveda available at the present era is derived from such sources. Thus, changing the history of Ayurveda from Oral to textual based knowledge is useful

for all generations.

The Bower Manuscripts, which date from the third century A.D., were discovered in 1890 by British Lieutenant Bower in Kuchiar, Chinese Turkestan. National Mission for Manuscripts (NMM), an independent agency within the Ministry of Culture, Government of India, was established in February 2003 and is the primary body for the gathering of manuscripts in India. It builds bibliographic databases and works on manuscript conservation and preservation. Online access to Ayurvedic Manuscripts is provided by IPGT & RA, Jamnagar. In addition to these, there are other Oriental libraries and research centres operating in India to preserve and conserve manuscripts. Other facilities include the Oriental Research Institute Library (Trivandrum, Vadodara, Chennai), Sarasvati Mahal Library, Kashi Sanskrit Visvavidyalaya, and the Library of Tibetan Works and Archives (HP) . It is difficult for academics to visit every single library in India. An option for these researchers is “Sanskrit Medical Manuscripts” in India, that Dr. Rama Rao published for CCRAS and provides references for the libraries in India that have copies of the manuscripts. Digitised versions of manuscripts gathered from various libraries across India are available at the Indira Gandhi National Centre for Arts in New Delhi and Bangalore.

All of these institutions and organisations aid in the cataloguing, identification, and preservation of unidentified manuscripts. Some of the most illustrious academics who worked in the area of Ayurvedic Manuscriptology were Acharya Yadavji Trikamji and Acharya P.V. Sharma. Numerous works that they edited and published are still used by academics today. Manuscriptology thus contributes to strengthening the Ayurvedic literary foundation by revealing the hidden knowledge that is mentioned in the manuscripts.

Conclusion

India is thought to have the greatest collection of manuscripts in the world, with an estimated five million manuscripts. Humans pose the greatest threat to the Manuscripts due to their inaction and negligence, yet they may also serve as the greatest guardians

if they act responsibly. Therefore, it is everyone's responsibility to safeguard and preserve it. The creation of a manuscript database and its cataloguing, preservation, and digitization should be the primary goals. For any person or institution engaged in research activity, the gathering and classification of research data is crucial. In reality, Manuscriptology is the art of feeling the pulse of the past. Manuscripts provide knowledge that will be useful to upcoming generations. In order to raise awareness of the importance of conserving and exploring manuscripts and to preserve the rich history of our country, there is a significant need to generate public interest in Manuscriptology through the organisation of exhibitions and workshops.

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KIRANĀVALĪ
Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation
The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XIV.
Book III-IV
JULY – DECEMBER 2022

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram-36
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